

Characterization of Cr implanted GaAs processed with ArF⁺ and Nd-YAG laser melting

Sari Algaidy^{1*}, Daniel Caudevillla², Rafael Benítez-Fernández², Sebastián Duarte-Cano², Francisco Perez-Zenteno², Rodrigo García-Hernansanz², Enrique San Andres², Eric García-Hemme², Javier Olea², Jan Siegel³, Jose Gonzalo³, David Pastor^{2*}, Alvaro del Prado^{2*}.

¹Instituto de Energía Solar, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, E.T.S.I. Telecomunicación, Ciudad Universitaria, 28040 Madrid, Spain.

²Dpt. Estructura de la Materia, Física Térmica y Electrónica, Fac. CC.Física, Univ. Complutense de Madrid, 28040, Spain.

³Laser Processing Group, Instituto de Óptica, IO-CSIC, Serrano 121, 28006, Madrid, Spain.

*corresponding authors: Sari.algaidy@alumnos.upm.es, adelprado@ucm.es, dpastor@ucm.es

Abstract— We present a detailed investigation on the properties of supersaturated GaAs using Cr implantation followed by nanosecond Pulsed Laser Melting (PLM). A comparison between two different lasers was carried out (ArF⁺ and Nd-YAG). We have analyzed supersaturated samples by means of structural, electrical, optical, and optoelectronic techniques. Raman spectroscopy results show a recovery of crystallinity after the PLM process. ToF-SIMS results reveal a Cr concentration above the solid solubility limit after the PLM process, featuring depth distribution depending on the type of laser used. The sheet resistance results obtained using van der Pauw configuration measurements show an activation of the implanted Cr in semi-insulating GaAs after PLM. Optical transmittance and Reflectance measurements show a sub-bandgap absorption (up to 10% for $\lambda = 1250$ nm) of the supersaturated GaAs:Cr related to the Cr incorporation, besides absorption induced by the PLM process itself. The origin of this sub-bandgap absorption has been analyzed by means of opto-electronic measurements revealing sub-bandgap photoresponsivity related to the absorption analyzed. The photoresponsivity measured below the bandgap originates from both the defects introduced by the PLM process and the states within the bandgap associated to the implanted Cr.

Index Terms—Gallium Arsenide, Ion implantation, Laser processing, Supersaturated Semiconductors.

1. INTRODUCTION

Hyperdoping semiconductors with deep level impurities is being extensively investigated in order to generate sub-bandgap photoresponse for solar cells and IR photodetectors. This response is possible due to the formation of a band of states within the semiconductor bandgap^[1-2]. The combination of ion implantation followed by pulsed laser melting (PLM) has been demonstrated to be a suitable technique to hyperdope semiconductors with impurities of concentrations above the insulator-to-metal limit^[3].

Several hyperdoped semiconductor systems such as, Si:InSb^[4], GaP^[5], InP^[6], Ge^[7] and GaN^[8] showed promising results in achieving absorption below bandgap and proof-of-concept of successfully obtaining an energy band that act as an intermediate band through high enough impurities insertion, using similar approaches. This helps toward the fabrication of photovoltaic and near-IR photodetection.

GaAs is a compound semiconductor of great interest for optoelectronics application. That is due to its ability to allow direct transition between the conduction and valence band. It also has been shown that, hyperdoping GaAs with transition metal ions also shows remarkable results in producing ferromagnetic properties that can be implemented toward spintronic technologies^[9-10].

In previous published papers ^[11-12], we characterized Ti supersaturated GaAs using multiple characterization techniques. The results showed a recovery of the crystallinity as well as an absorption in the subbandgap (up to 6.5% for $\lambda = 1000$ nm) region that was associated with point defects induced by the PLM process. Furthermore, no electrical activation was observed.

In this paper, we are aiming to obtain a sub-bandgap photoresponse in Cr implanted GaAs while examining the effect of two different lasers (ArF⁺ excimer laser and Nd-YAG laser) in the previously observed point defect. Structural, optical, electrical and optoelectronic characterization of Cr supersaturated GaAs was conducted.

The results showed a recovery of the crystallinity after the implantation and PLM process along with the incorporation of Cr to achieve a high enough concentration to exceed the insulator-to-metal limit. Furthermore, a clear sub-bandgap absorption for PLM processed samples, where Nd-YAG laser showed a more intense absorption. For the implanted samples, an absorption has been observed that relate to the implanted Cr and correlate directly with the implanted dose, up to 10% for $\lambda = 1250$ nm. An electrical activation of Cr has been demonstrated using sheet resistane measurements in combination with Hall effect. This is also reflected on the results for the photoresponse obtained in the optoelectronics characterization for the just PLM sample and the sample processed with ArF⁺ excimer laser.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

Undoped n-type semi-insulating GaAs grown in the <100> direction, double sided polished, 650 μm of thickness with a resistivity of $2.2 \times 10^8 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$ at room temperature and mobility of $4000 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ was implanted in a refurbished VARIAN CF3000 ion implanter with a ⁵²Cr⁺ dose of $2 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (**low dose**) and $4 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (**high dose**) at energy of 32 keV. The implantation was conducted using a 7° tilt angle, to reduce channelling ^[13].

A set of samples were irradiated with an ArF⁺ excimer pulsed laser ($\lambda = 193$ nm, with a pulse duration of 20 ns full width half maximum) and another set with a Nd-YAG pulsed laser ($\lambda = 355$ nm, with a pulse duration of 4 ns full width half maximum) in ambient air. The pulse laser melting fluence used was 0.50 J/cm^2 . The laser beam was homogenized in a square spot area of $1 \times 1 \text{ mm}^2$ for the ArF⁺ excimer laser and $3 \times 3 \text{ mm}^2$ for the Nd-YAG pulsed laser on the sample surface. The total sample area ($1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$ or $2 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$, depending on the characterization technique) was processed by overlapping single pulses across the irradiation plane. Just PLM processed non-implanted GaAs, as well as as-implanted samples were also prepared as control samples.

The crystal quality of the implanted samples was analyzed by Raman scattering spectroscopy using an Olympus BXFM microscope equipped with a coupled charge detector model AndoriDus DU-420 Peltier cooled. The scattered light was recorded at room temperature in unpolarized backscattering configuration using a 532 nm laser with a power of 22mW. Multiple points were sampled randomly across the surface of the samples for averaging.

The depth concentration profile of Cr in the GaAs samples was obtained by ToF-SIMS measurements using an ION-TOF-SIMS model IV. The area of interest selected for the SIMS measurements was inside a single

irradiation pulse. This way we avoided the overlapping area, which receives more than one pulse, and therefore maximised the accuracy of the ToF-SIMS profile. The sputtering beam creates a $450 \times 450 \mu\text{m}^2$ spot size. However, the analysed area was slightly smaller ($250 \times 250 \mu\text{m}^2$), to avoid crater edge effects. The primary pulsed ion beam consisted of Bi^{3+} with incident energy of 25 keV and an O_2^+ sputtering gun was used with an energy of 1 keV. Both ion beam and sputtering gun were tilted at a 45° angle. As-implanted samples were also analysed using ToF-SIMS for calibration purposes. The crater depth was characterized by optical profilometry using white light interferometry and a constant erosion rate was assumed for the sputtering gun. The ToF-SIMS was conducted under high-vacuum environment of 3.1×10^{-8} mbar.

For optical characterization of the recrystallized layer, transmittance $T(\lambda)$ and reflectance $R(\lambda)$ (in specular mode) spectra in the range 400 to 2500 nm were obtained using a UV/VIS/NIR PerkinElmer Lambda 1050 spectrometer. The measured transmittance and reflectance data have been normalized to correct calibration inaccuracies of the measurements, so that $T+R$ equals 100% in the region where no absorption takes place, following the same procedure described in ^[12]. For samples absorbing over the whole measured range, the same correction factors were applied (1.01 for T and 1.02 for R). The results were used to obtain the absorption coefficient and refractive index of the processed layers using a modification of the incoherent limit for the T and R equations, described in ^[14], as detailed below.

After the laser melting process, a set of the samples was prepared for electrical characterization with the van der Pauw set-up. Triangular ohmic metal contacts were deposited on the corners of $1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$ square samples by Joule evaporation of an Au:Ge (88:12 ratio) layer of 100 nm thickness, and subsequently an e-beam evaporation of a 200 nm Au layer, without breaking the vacuum. The recipe used for the contacts can be found in the literature ^[15,16].

The van der Pauw configuration was used to perform two different types of measurements. Firstly, the sheet resistance of the samples was measured in darkness at room temperature using a Keithley 4200 SCS equipped with four source and measure units, four configurations for current injection and measured voltage are used, with positive and negative current for each configuration. The sheet resistance is obtained as the mean value. The mobility and carrier concentration were also obtained by Hall effect measurements using four configurations, positive and negative magnetic field (0.9 T) and positive and negative current. Results are obtained as the mean value of the 16 configurations measured to avoid undesired thermo-galvanometric effects.

Secondly, the spectral photoresponsivity of the samples was measured. A Keithley 2636 current source was configured to feed 100 nA between two of the contacts. The AC photogenerated voltage was obtained with a Stanford SR-830 DSP dual phase lock-in amplifier. However, due to the high resistivity of the samples, an INA111AP instrumentation amplifier was used to increase the input impedance of the lock-in amplifier. A UV-Vis-NIR Horiba IHR320 spectrophotometer with a 250 W tungsten halogen lamp was used as a light source. A chopper was configured to produce AC illumination at 23Hz. Finally, the spectral power density of the light impinging on the sample was measured with a calibrated Si S2281 Hamamatsu photodiode in photovoltaic mode. All the samples measured were injected with a constant 100 nA current, except the reference sample which was injected with a 20 nA current.

The following equation shows the basic parameters of interest to obtain the photoresponsivity:

$$R_{(sample)}(\lambda) = \frac{V_{(sample)}(\lambda)}{P(\lambda) \times A_{(sample)}} \quad (1)$$

$$P(\lambda) = \frac{V_{(sensor)}(\lambda)}{R_{(sensor)}(\lambda) \times A_{(sensor)}} \quad (2)$$

Where $R_{(sample)}(\lambda)$ is the measured responsivity as a function of the wavelength of the sample and $R_{(sensor)}(\lambda)$ is the given responsivity by the manufacturer, as a function of wavelength of the detector, respectively, $V_{(sample)}(\lambda)$ and $V_{(sensor)}(\lambda)$ are the measured voltage of the sample and the detector as a function of wavelength, respectively, produced by the light illumination and measured by the lock-in, $P(\lambda)$ is the incident optical power density, and $A_{(sample)}$ and $A_{(sensor)}$ are the area of the sample and detector, respectively.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Structural Characterization

Figure 1 shows the Raman spectra of four samples (reference, as-implanted, implanted and processed by PLM at 0.50 J/cm^2 with two different lasers). The reference sample shows the crystalline peak reflecting the LO-mode located at 292 cm^{-1} [17]. The TO-mode can also be observed in all the samples due to residual contribution out of plane in the backscattering configuration [18]. After implantation, the characteristic broadband associated to amorphous GaAs is observed at approximately 250 cm^{-1} [19]. This broadband is consistent with the high implantation dose used ($2 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (not shown here) and $4 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) [19].

Figure 1 Raman spectroscopy of GaAs reference, as-implanted GaAs:Cr, implanted GaAs:Cr with high dose and processed with ArF⁺ excimer laser and implanted GaAs:Cr with high dose and processed with Nd-YAG laser.

After the PLM process (for both lasers) the amorphous band disappears and the LO-mode is recovered, which indicates that the PLM fluence used is sufficient to recover the crystalline quality after implantation. The notable difference is in between the reference sample and the processed samples which is a redshift associated with tensile strain produced by the Cr incorporation and PLM process^[20]. Similar results were reported for Ti supersaturated GaAs^[11]. The Raman results indicate a high crystalline quality after the PLM process.

Figure 2 shows the ToF-SIMS results along with the impurity profile distribution simulated using Stopping and Range of Ions in Matter (SRIM) package^[21]. The simulation predicts the ion depth distribution in an amorphous semiconductor system, using typical parameters, such as implanted dose, implantation energy, etc. The 7° tilt angle used during implantation in the crystalline samples results in an amorphous-like distribution of the ions. The total areas of the ToF-SIMS and SRIM were normalized to the implanted dose. The expected gaussian depth-profile distribution of Cr is in agreement with the SRIM simulations. For the samples processed with ArF⁺ and samples processed with Nd-YAG laser, the concentration has been estimated assuming the same relationship between counts and the concentration of the as-implanted sample for both doses, separately. Since the as-implanted sample is amorphous and the PLM processed samples recover the crystallinity, these concentrations should be considered as estimations, since the ionization rate can be affected by the structure of the sample. The estimated Cr concentration is obtained by dividing the total implanted dose by the area of integration of the as-implanted sample (of the same dose) and multiplying it by the count obtained through the ToF-SIMS measurements. For both lasers, a layer where the Cr concentration is above the theoretical insulator to metal transition limits (approximately $5.9 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ ^[3]) is observed with a thicknesses of approximately 25 nm for the low dose and 40 nm for the high dose. Furthermore, the solid solubility limit of Cr in GaAs, at the melting point of undoped GaAs (1238 °C) is approximately $2 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ ^[22], which is significantly lower than the maximum obtained concentration ($2 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-3}$). An estimation of the remaining implanted Cr for both doses and both lasers can be calculated by dividing the area integration of implanted and PLM sample with the associated as-implanted sample. The estimated remaining percentage of Cr obtained for the low dose implanted samples correspond to 90% and 69% laser melted by ArF⁺ excimer laser and Nd-YAG laser, respectively, and for the high dose implanted samples correspond to 69% and 64% laser melted by ArF⁺ excimer laser and Nd-YAG laser, respectively.

The laser energy fluence used for both lasers has been chosen due to previously published results^[11], to ensure melting the whole implanted layer and reaching the crystalline substrate beyond, to recrystallize with the underlying crystalline seed during the solidification process. The melting depth was obtained using a simulation tool LIMP (Laser Induced Melting Prediction, check supplementary document figure S1).

Figure 2 SRIM simulation and ToF-SIMS measurements of as-implanted GaAs:Cr with two different doses (low dose and high dose) and implanted GaAs:Cr processed with two different lasers (ArF⁺ excimer and Nd-YAG).

After the PLM process, a clear redistribution of the impurities can be seen. The Cr accumulates near the surface with a sharp peak-shaped distribution up to a given depth, and then the concentration decreases with a much lower slope, extending even beyond the as-implanted depth. To better understand the behaviour of Cr redistribution after the PLM process, we need to consider the dynamics of the laser melting process. In the first step, the whole amorphous implanted layer and part of the underlying crystalline layer is melted. In this liquid phase the impurities tend to redistribute by diffusion toward lower concentration regions, particularly, deeper toward the liquid/solid interface. In the second step, the melted region rapidly recrystallize, starting from the seed of the substrate underneath the implanted region, the highest solid solubility of the liquid phase respect to the solid phase, produce the out diffusion of the impurities to the liquid phase during the melt from re-solidification, and an increase of the impurities in the close surface region.

It must be remarked that the depth of the maximum of the Cr concentration is significantly different for both lasers used. For the samples processed with ArF⁺ excimer laser the maximum of the Cr concentration is approximately 2 nm from the surface, while for sample processed with Nd-YAG laser the peak maximum stands at approximately 8 nm from the surface.

B. Optical Characterization

Figure 3 shows the normalized absorptance obtained from the measured transmittance and reflectance for the GaAs reference, two samples processed with the ArF⁺ and Nd-YAG lasers at fluence of 0.50 J/cm² and implanted sample and subsequently processed with the two lasers at two different implantation doses (2×10¹⁵ cm⁻² and 4×10¹⁵ cm⁻²). The inset shows a detail of the below bandgap region.

Figure 3 Absorbance of GaAs reference, GaAs processed with PLM using two different lasers (ArF⁺ excimer and Nd-YAG), implanted GaAs:Cr with two different doses (low dose and high dose) processed with two different lasers (ArF⁺ excimer and Nd-YAG).

For all the samples, the expected absorption edge corresponding to the GaAs direct bandgap at (880 nm) is observed. It is important to notice that the GaAs reference shows an absorption right below the bandgap up to approximately 1100 nm. This absorption can only be attributed to defects present in the reference sample. Note that, although the observed absorbance value is significant, the corresponding absorption coefficient would be averaged over the whole thickness of the sample (650 μm), leading to a value orders of magnitude lower than the absorption coefficients corresponding to the processed layers. For the non-implanted sample processed with the ArF⁺ excimer laser, an increase of the absorbance right below the bandgap is observed, but absorbance remains zero for higher wavelengths. The non-implanted sample processed with the Nd-YAG laser shows a much higher increase in absorbance and extended over the whole measured range, indicating a significant modification of the sample with respect to the ArF⁺ laser, which is consistent with the higher energy density applied to the sample (same fluence with a small pulse duration, i.e. higher power density). For the implanted samples, for both lasers, a further increase of the absorbance is observed with respect to the just PLM processed sample. Besides, the increase correlates with the implanted dose clearly indicating that this absorbance is related to the incorporation of Cr.

In the region above the bandgap, we observe a decrease of the absorbance for the Cr implanted samples (more pronounced for the Nd-YAG processed samples) with respect to the reference and non-implanted samples. In this region transmittance becomes zero ($T = 0$) because the substrate absorbing the whole signal and the shown absorbance corresponds to just $A = 1 - R$, with R being determined just by the first reflection between air and the processed sample (no multiple reflections at the back of the sample contribute to R in this region because

of the substrate absorbing the whole signal). According to our results, the presence of Cr seems to enhance this reflectance, which would be related to a modification of the refractive index.

To obtain the optical parameters of the processed layer, a two layers model for the sample with front and back air layers has been used, following the method described in ^[12] for Ti supersaturated GaAs based on the incoherent approach given in ^[14]. Yet, some corrections to the model have been introduced to consider possible variations of the refractive index of the processed layer with respect to the substrate. The two layers model is schematically shown in figure 4.

According to the Cr profiles shown in figure 2, where the Cr concentration gradually decreases from the surface of the processed layer until reaching the non-processed substrate, and taking into account the absorptance results relating the refractive index value to the presence of Cr, we consider a graded refractive index value in the processed layer from n_{2a} value at the surface to the value of the substrate at this interface ($n_{2b} = n_3$). According to this approach, no reflectance will take place at the interface between the processed layer (layer 2) and the substrate (layer 3).

The resulting equations for T and R are ^[11, 13]:

$$R_{GaAs+PLM} = |r_{12}|^2 + \frac{|t_{12}|^2 |t_{21}|^2 |r_{34}|^2 e^{-2\alpha_2 t_2} e^{-2\alpha_3 t_3}}{1 - |r_{21}|^2 |r_{34}|^2 e^{-2\alpha_2 t_2} e^{-2\alpha_3 t_3}} \quad (3)$$

$$T_{GaAs+PLM} = \frac{|N_{2a}|}{|N_3|} |t_{12}|^2 |t_{34}|^2 \frac{e^{-\alpha_2 t_2} e^{-\alpha_3 t_3}}{1 - |r_{21}|^2 |r_{34}|^2 e^{-2\alpha_2 t_2} e^{-2\alpha_3 t_3}} \quad (4)$$

Where t_{ij} and r_{ij} are the Fresnel coefficients and the modules of the complex refractive indexes ($N = n - ik$) are considered for computing the energy in absorbing medium ^[23]. Yet, in the sub-bandgap region analyzed, the contribution of k is almost negligible and $|N| \approx n$. The absorption coefficient in the processed layer will also be expected to change gradually. The $\alpha_2 t_2$ term in equation 3 and 4 corresponds to the integrated absorption coefficient over the processed layer: $\alpha_2 t_2 = \int_0^{t_2} \alpha(z) dz$.

For the substrate the R and T equations simplify and substrate parameter (layer 3) are obtained from the measured reference T and R as detailed in ^[12]. For the processed samples, the fitting parameters are $\alpha_2 t_2$ and n_{2a} as a function of the wavelength. The fitting is limited to the 890 nm – 2500 nm wavelength range because of the absorption of the substrate becoming too high for lower wavelengths resulting in null transmittance. According to the LIMP simulations, a thickness of 120 nm was used for the processed layers. This thickness is only relevant to compute k_2 from $\alpha_2 t_2$ for calculating the Fresnel coefficients. Yet, in the analyzed range, we have always obtained $k_2 \ll n_{2a}$ so that inaccuracy in the actual processed layer thickness has a negligible impact in the fittings.

Figure 4 Two-layer model for optical analysis. Where n_2 and n_3 is the refractive index of the processed layer and the substrate respectively and α_2 and α_3 is the absorption coefficient of the processed layer and the substrate, respectively.

Since two parameters are calculated for each wavelength from two equations, a perfect fitting of the model to the results is obtained. The fitting results for the PLM processed sample and the implanted GaAs:Cr at high dose and PLM processed samples using the two different lasers are shown in the supplementary material as an example in figure S2.

Figure 5 shows the obtained refractive index for all the samples. It is remarkable that for the non-implanted ArF⁺ excimer laser processed sample the obtained refractive index is essentially the same as the obtained for the substrate, even though no restriction or dispersion rule was imposed for the fitting of the experimental results. This supports the previously published results ^[12] where no change in the refractive index was considered for the PLM processed samples using this specific laser. Besides, it also demonstrates the consistency of the model used. For the non-implanted sample processed with the Nd-YAG laser, a slight increase of the refractive index with respect to the substrate is observed, indicating a modification of the substrate.

Figure 5 The calculated refractive index of all the samples.

Figure 6 shows the resulting exponential factor a_2t_2 (product of the absorption coefficient with thickness) for all the samples (substrate, GaAs + PLM only, GaAs:Cr low dose and GaAs:Cr high dose) processed with ArF⁺ excimer and Nd-YAG laser as a function of energy. The abrupt increase observed at approximately 1.41 eV for all samples is due to the absorption edge of GaAs. For the reference sample, it is important to note that the considered thickness is (650 μm). At lower energy (eV < 0.8) the values of the absorption coefficient is zero, an increase can be observed related to point defects in the reference sample. For the GaAs + PLM sample processed with ArF⁺ excimer laser, no absorption is observed below 0.9 eV. Above this energy, a roughly exponential behaviour is observed. This behaviour has been previously observed and reported and is characteristic of defective crystalline GaAs with point defects or clusters of point defects (vacancies, antisite defects and vacancy-antisite complexes) responsible of this absorption [12, 24, 25]. For the non-implanted sample processed with Nd-YAG laser, an absorption is observed through the whole range. This absorption is similar to the absorption observed in the implanted samples; however, they originate from a combination of different point defects or clusters of point defects.

Figure 6 Absorption Coefficient as a function of energy for reference substrate sample, a sample processed by PLM, a sample implanted with Cr at low dose and a sample implanted with Cr at high dose and processed with PLM using ArF⁺ excimer and Nd-YAG laser.

As for the Cr implanted samples processed with both lasers, a higher αt value is observed with respect to the non-implanted PLM processed samples and extending over the whole energy range. Besides, the increasing behaviour of α when increasing the energy is the opposite to the expected behaviour for free carrier absorption [26, 27]. Figure 7 shows the increase of the absorption coefficient with respect to the just PLM processed samples ($\alpha_{Cr+PLM} - \alpha_{PLM}$). A correlation with the dose measured with ToF-SIMS is observed. For the high dose implanted samples, considering a thickness 40 nm for the Cr supersaturated layer, high values of the absorption coefficient ranging from $1.0 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 0.5 eV to $2.3 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 1.36 eV are obtained. Similar absorption has been observed for other hyperdoped semiconductors and attributed to the formation of a band of state within the bandgap [6, 28]. We conclude that the same mechanism is taking place in our GaAs:Cr samples.

Figure 7 influence of Cr on the absorption coefficient as a function of energy for a sample implanted with Cr at low dose and a sample implanted with Cr at high dose and processed with PLM using ArF⁺ excimer and Nd-YAG laser.

C. Electrical and Optoelectronic Characterization

Table 1 shows the electrical parameters obtained at room temperature. Uncertainty is calculated as the standard deviation (σ_{N-1}) of the measurements in all configurations divided by the square root of the number of configurations. The uncertainty in the sheet resistance measurements of the reference sample and the Cr implanted samples is high because of the dispersion of the measured results at the different configurations. For the reference, the non-implanted samples and the low dose sample processed with ArF⁺ excimer laser, n-type mobility was observed according to the Hall effect measurements. The mobility and sheet carrier concentrations were calculated assuming conductivity is due to electrons. For the other samples, the values of the Hall voltage were too low, below the calculated uncertainty, and it was not possible to determine the mobility and sheet carrier concentration. The reference sample shows a very high sheet resistance and very low carrier concentration, one order of magnitude above the intrinsic value (considering the 650 μm thickness of the substrate)^[27]. The non-implanted sample processed with ArF⁺ excimer laser shows a slight decrease in the mobility while the sheet resistance and sheet carrier concentrations are similar to the reference sample, indicating a high recrystallization quality after the melting. The decrease of the mobility is consistent with the absorption results related to point defects present in this sample. The non-implanted sample processed with Nd-YAG laser shows a one order of magnitude lowering of the sheet resistance and a significant reduction of the mobility, while the sheet carrier concentration is increased by 3 orders of magnitude, indicating a significant modification of the sample induced by the PLM process itself, this also has been observed in the optical characterization. The results indicate that the defects introduced by the Nd-YAG laser are electrically active, contributing to an increase in the sheet carrier concentration. Given the decrease of the sheet resistance

we can consider that the electrical properties measured are essentially those of the processed layer. Considering the simulated 120 nm depth penetration of the laser, the carrier concentration in this layer would be around 10^{14} cm^{-3} . All the Cr implanted, and PLM processed samples show a clear electrical activation of the Cr implantation, with a decrease of the sheet resistance of up to 4 orders of magnitude, being this decrease more pronounced for the high dose samples. For the low dose sample processed with ArF⁺ excimer laser, considering a thickness of 20 nm, according to the ToF-SIMS results for the hyperdoped layer, a high value of the carrier concentration of $1.8 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ is obtained. Yet, this value is orders of magnitude below the actual Cr concentration measured by ToF-SIMS. For the other Cr implanted samples, although it was not possible to calculate neither the sheet carrier concentration nor the mobility, the mobility is not expected to be higher than in the low dose sample processed with ArF⁺ excimer laser and given the lower measured sheet resistance values, the carrier concentration would be up to nearly two orders of magnitude higher for the high implanted dose. These results, together with the previously shown optical results, demonstrate the possibility to hyperdoping GaAs with Cr with both electrical activation and sub-bandgap absorption, in contrast with previously published results for Ti supersaturated GaAs where neither electrical nor absorption response was measured associated to the presence of Ti [12].

Table 1 Electrical results obtained by Hall measurements under van der Pauw condition at room temperature.

Sample (PLM:0.50 J/cm ²)	Sheet Resistance (Ω/sqr)	Mobility ($\text{cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$)	Sheet Carrier Concentration (cm^{-2})
GaAs Reference	$(6.9 \pm 2.0) \times 10^8$	$(4.7 \pm 1.4) \times 10^3$	$(1.8 \pm 0.13) \times 10^6$
GaAs+PLM ArF ⁺	$(5.5 \pm 1.5) \times 10^8$	$(3.1 \pm 0.8) \times 10^3$	$(3.6 \pm 0.14) \times 10^6$
GaAs+PLM Nd-YAG	$(3.8 \pm 0.7) \times 10^7$	$(6.8 \pm 3.2) \times 10^1$	$(1.2 \pm 0.1) \times 10^9$
GaAs:Cr ArF ⁺ ($2 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$)	$(1.3 \pm 0.6) \times 10^6$	(3.2 ± 1.6)	$(3.2 \pm 1.2) \times 10^{12}$
GaAs:Cr Nd-YAG ($2 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$)	$(1.0 \pm 0.6) \times 10^5$	×	×
GaAs:Cr ArF ⁺ ($4 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$)	$(1.7 \pm 0.9) \times 10^4$	×	×
GaAs:Cr Nd-YAG ($4 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$)	$(1.1 \pm 0.7) \times 10^4$	×	×

× = couldn't be measured accurately, relatively high error rate.

Figure 8 shows the calibrated spectral response of the reference sample, and the non-implanted and low dose PLM processed samples, for both lasers. The results for the high dose samples are similar to the implanted Nd-YAG processed sample. For the reference sample, the expected abrupt increase of the photo-response for energies above the bandgap ($\lambda < 880 \text{ nm}$; $h\nu > 1.43 \text{ eV}$) is observed. The values below the bandgap are in the noise level of the measurements. This can be confirmed by observing the phase provided by the lock-in amplifier, with no stable values (shown in figure S3 in the supplementary material).

For just PLM processed samples, a very strong photo-response is observed below the bandgap (with a consistent signal of the phase obtained from the lock-in amplifier as shown in figure S3 in the supplementary material). This result was previously reported for GaAs processed by PLM using the ArF⁺ excimer laser. The same result is now found for the Nd-YAG laser, even though the modification to the GaAs induced by this laser is much different from the point of view of optical and electrical properties, as previously discussed.

As for the Cr implanted and PLM processed samples, only the low dose sample processed with ArF⁺ excimer laser shows photo-response below the bandgap ($\lambda > 880 \text{ nm}$). While this is not evident in figure 7, looking at the signal of the phase provided by the lock-in, we can observe a stable value of the phase in the below bandgap region for this sample (unlike the reference sample and the sample processed with Nd-YAG laser,

which were in the noise level, note that the noise level is not the same for the different samples). Regarding the low dose sample implanted and processed with Nd-YAG laser, and the high dose samples (not shown in figure 8), no photo-response was observed below the bandgap. For these samples, the darkness sheet resistance is lower and, therefore, for a given current, the change in voltage associated to a given change in conductivity is smaller.

Figure 8 Calibrated photoresponsivity of GaAs reference, GaAs laser annealed at 0.50 J/cm^2 and implanted and laser annealed GaAs:Cr at 0.50 J/cm^2 fluence for ArF⁺ excimer laser and Nd-YAG laser.

Due to the difference in darkness sheet resistance of the samples, for comparison, we need to explore the actual change in conductivity. The darkness sheet resistance (R_d) for a uniform sample in the van der Pauw configuration is given by ^[29]:

$$R_d = \frac{1}{G_d} = \frac{\pi}{\ln 2} \times \frac{V_d}{I} \quad (5)$$

Where G_d is the sheet conductance in darkness, V_d is the measured voltage in darkness and I is the applied current. Under illumination, working at constant injected current, the measured voltage will change to $V_{il} = V_d - \Delta V$, where ΔV is the measured voltage (module). Therefore, considering $\Delta V / V_d \ll I$, we can obtain the change in conductance as:

$$\Delta G_{il} = G_d \left(\frac{\Delta V}{V_d} \right) \quad (6)$$

Considering the previous equations, we can re-write the sheet photoconductance as follows:

$$\Delta G_{il} = G_d^2 \times \frac{\pi}{I \ln 2} \times \Delta V = \frac{\pi}{I \ln 2} \times \frac{\Delta V}{Rd^2} \quad (7)$$

Being the change in conductance proportional to the measured change in voltage, we can obtain the change in conductance per incident power using the calibrated photo-response (V/W) as ΔV in equation 7. Table 2 shows the calculated sheet photoconductance by using Eq (7) below the bandgap at wavelength 1090 nm.

Table 2 Calculated sheet photoconductance below bandgap.

Samples at 1090 nm	Calibrated Photo-response (V/W)	Darkness Sheet Resistance (Ω/sqr)	Calibrated Sheet photoconductance (S/W)
GaAs+PLM ArF ⁺	1.1×10^3	$(5.5 \pm 1.5) \times 10^8$	$(1.65 \pm 0.39) \times 10^{-7}$
GaAs+PLM Nd-YAG	3.7×10^2	$(3.8 \pm 0.7) \times 10^7$	$(1.40 \pm 0.24) \times 10^{-5}$
GaAs:Cr ArF ⁺ ($2 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$)	1.4×10^{-1}	$(1.3 \pm 0.6) \times 10^6$	$(3.61 \pm 1.41) \times 10^{-6}$

For the non-implanted ArF⁺ excimer laser processed sample, the observed photoconductance is attributed to transitions involving states within the bandgap associated to the induced defects. These defects do not only produce sub-bandgap absorption, but this absorption translates into actual carrier photogeneration and a very significant sub-bandgap photoconductance. For the non-implanted Nd-YAG processed sample, a similar defect generation mechanism during PLM is expected. Yet, the concentration of defects must be higher, given the higher absorptance, and part of the induced defects is acting as donors, increasing the electron carrier concentration. This is consistent with higher power applied to the sample by this laser.

Besides, the sub-bandgap photoconductance is higher in the sample processed with this laser, in good agreement with the higher absorption coefficient obtained. The relative increase in conductance $\Delta G_{il}/G_d$ is also higher for this sample. Thus, the Nd-YAG laser processing arises as an interesting technique due to the combined capability of producing sub-bandgap photo-response and an n-type character of the substrate, which could be useful to fabricate junction devices. For the Cr implanted and processed with ArF⁺ excimer laser, the actual change in conductance is higher than in the non-implanted sample, indicating a contribution of the absorption associated to Cr states to sub-bandgap photoconductance. The relative photoconductance with respect to darkness conductance decreases with respect to the non-implanted sample. Yet, the high sheet carrier concentration in this sample indicates an n-type behaviour associated to Cr which would also be of interest for junction device fabrication.

4. CONCLUSION

In this work, semi-insulating GaAs was implanted with Cr ions at a dose of 2×10^{15} and $4 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and subsequently processed by pulsed laser melting, at a specific fluence of 0.50 J/cm^2 using two different lasers (ArF⁺ excimer laser and Nd-YAG laser). Both lasers achieved a good recovery of the crystalline structure as demonstrated by Raman spectroscopy. ToF-SIMS measurements revealed the presence of hyperdoped GaAs:Cr layers with Cr concentrations over the insulator-to-metal limit, whose thickness (20 nm to 40 nm) were depending on the dose. The optical results showed a significant sub-bandgap absorption for non-implanted, PLM processed samples, which we attribute to the formation of point defects during the laser

melting and solidification process. This absorption was higher and extended over a larger wavelength range for Nd-YAG laser, which we attribute to the higher peak power and faster quench rates achieved with this laser as a result of the shorter pulse duration (4 ns versus 20 ns). This laser also produced a significant modification of the electrical properties of the sample, with a significant decrease of the mobility and an increase of the electron sheet carrier concentration. On the other hand, for the ArF⁺ excimer laser, mobility and sheet carrier concentration remained in the same order of magnitude as in the reference substrate. Significant sub-bandgap photoconductivity was also observed for both lasers, being higher for the Nd-YAG laser in terms of absolute value (ΔG_{it}) and relative to darkness value ($\Delta G_{it} / G_d$). For Cr implanted samples, an enhanced sub-bandgap absorption was observed, which correlates with the implanted Cr dose, making it clear that the implantation of Cr produces optically active states within the bandgap. The implanted Cr also led to an increase of the electron sheet carrier density together with a strong decrease of mobility and an overall decrease of the sheet resistance (reaching the lowest values for the higher implanted dose). For the ArF⁺ excimer laser processed sample it was also possible to demonstrate sub-bandgap photoresponse for the sample implanted with the lower dose. The measured value increases with respect to the non-implanted, PLM-processed sample; although the increase relative to the darkness value is smaller. In summary, we have demonstrated the possibility to hyperdope GaAs with Cr using ion implantation followed by pulsed laser melting, triggering optical and electrical activation as well as sub-bandgap photoresponse. This process could be used for the fabrication of junction devices with an extended photo-response below the bandgap.

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